

When considering the UK's future force design, to what extent do ethical, perceptual, and cross-domain liabilities constrain the value of uninhabited aircraft and their systems?

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Abstract

This paper examines the liabilities associated with uninhabited aircraft (UA) and their systems (UAS) within the context of the United Kingdom's future military force design. It analyses how ethical, perceptual, regulatory, and cross-domain factors shape the operational value and integration of these technologies. The study argues that limited integration into civil airspace, unresolved ethical questions surrounding remote and autonomous operations, and public concern over surveillance and lethal autonomy represent significant non-technical barriers to adoption. At the same time, growing commercial uptake of UA offers opportunities to improve flexibility and reduce procurement costs, provided regulatory frameworks evolve accordingly. The paper further highlights the increasing dependence of UAS on space and cyber domains, identifying vulnerabilities in positioning, navigation, timing, and communications that complicate future force resilience. It contends that effective exploitation of UA will require pan-domain command and control, a coherent taxonomy of autonomy, and the development of internationally credible ethical and legal norms. The paper concludes that while uninhabited systems offer substantial strategic advantages, their successful integration into future force structures depends as much on regulatory leadership, ethical governance, and public legitimacy as on technological advancement.

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Introduction

Drones have variously been depicted by the mainstream media as: dystopian killer robots with a unique nature of their own; ubiquitous threats to privacy; futuristic replacements for local delivery agents; and, dangerous toys putting airline passengers at risk. Whichever the characterisation, uninhabited aircraft (UA) seem to capture the popular zeitgeist. Unencumbered by human occupants, UA exploit technology from space and cyber, often with a distinctly science fiction bent. All types are undeniably proliferating at pace. Some industry estimates suggest UA will expand the total number of aircraft by a quarter within five years¹. Armed Forces around the world are expected to buy more than 80,000 surveillance UA and 2,000 attack UA by 2029.² Political leaders in Britain envision that by 2040, only ten percent of UK combat aircraft will be manned³.

Given the huge variation in types and character it can be hard to define and categorise the field, but such distinctions are vital to a clear understanding of their use and integration with other air users. Developing such an understanding is recognised as a key challenge for the UK Ministry of Defence (MOD)⁴. It is also evident that UA interact with capability derived from the cyber and space domains in novel ways, making it important to understand the extent to which adverse activity in space or cyberspace could constrain the value of such systems. Whilst the UK Joint Doctrine Paper 30.2⁵ describes in broad terms the definitions and utility of UA, there is less to synergise this with the developing doctrine relating to managing cross-domain activity and risks, or ethical and perceptual challenges which may in future be exacerbated by improved autonomy. This paper will explore these issues from a UK perspective, to provide an insight into contingent liabilities for UA in a future force.

How do we term an aircraft without a human occupant?

The first challenge in understanding this subject is one of semantics. Terminology is inconsistent⁶. Whilst confusing, this is to be expected as it is borne of etymological differences amongst respective communities (in particular, regionally and by user-group). It results from attempts to accurately distinguish between specific characteristics and capabilities of given platforms.

The term Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) is decreasing in popularity as it does not do justice to the complex web of systems necessary to support and exploit the aircraft capability, nor does it accurately reflect the requirement for any aircraft which is not fully autonomous to be operated by crew, albeit remotely. ‘Unmanned’ suggests a degree of autonomy that current systems lack, so many regulatory provisions now refer to those flown with real-time input from qualified crews as ‘remotely piloted’. A more comprehensive descriptor, encompassing both platforms with increased autonomy and those requiring real-time input, might be ‘uninhabited’. The other descriptor, ‘aircraft’ vice ‘air system’ (or ‘aerial system’), neatly captures the distinction between the vehicle itself and the broader system of datalinks, coding and engineering that supports remote or autonomous flight. These broader systems allow the real-time exploitation of intelligence – legacy

¹ Airbus, as cited by Topham (2019)

² *Janes Market Forecast*, as cited by Sabbagh (2019)

³ Wallace, B. (2020)

⁴ House of Commons Library Briefing Paper 06493 (2015), as cited in JDP 0-30.2

⁵ UK MOD (2017) *Joint Doctrine Paper 0-30.2 (Change 1)*

⁶ University of Nottingham (2017) p1; JDP0-30.2 p12

platforms frequently had to have their data physically recovered and processed after a sortie was completed. This paper will use Uninhabited Aircraft (UA) to describe all aircraft without a human occupant. Uninhabited Aircraft System (UAS) will be used where the broader system of datalinks and networks supporting the UA is directly relevant. Remotely Piloted Aircraft (RPA) or Remotely Piloted Aircraft System (RPAS) will be used when describing such aircraft flown in real-time by a qualified human crew. Whilst avoiding the term unmanned, this is otherwise consistent with NATO and UK doctrine⁷. When citing a source, this paper will use the term used by the author of the source.

Why are UAS proliferating?

Fundamentally, UAS are proliferating because they are cheaper or offer new opportunities. Savings in hardware and per-hour costs for a given capability, when compared to legacy platforms, are derived from relative simplicity, improved endurance, or exploitation of networked information advantage. In future, automatic cooperative flight without human input will allow UA to act as 'loyal wingmen' and conduct 'swarm activity'. This is likely to create advantages over manned systems, particularly for military operations in contested airspace. From a human resource perspective, automatic and autonomous operations have potential to create efficiencies for operators in training and manpower costs. In the context of operations with high risk-to-life (RtL), UA mitigate immediate physical risk to the lives of their operators. For example, in a military context they may create opportunities for operational exploitation by deploying into contested circumstances where an aircraft occupied by a person might lead to loss of life and a political imperative for escalation. In turn, this renders UA attractive for what military and political theorists' term 'sub-threshold' or 'grey zone' activity (activity outside that condoned by the traditional rules-based-system of international relations and below the threshold for conventional war).

It is unsurprising given concomitant reductions in political, social, and financial costs, that UA are becoming increasingly prevalent in conflicts worldwide. Commercially certifiable platforms are beginning to emerge, suggesting forthcoming improvements in integration to civil, unsegregated airspace⁸. This will be a boon for both existing operators and those looking into future use-cases. It will engender flexibility of operation for Defence platforms, with UAS equally able to support peacetime objectives in unsegregated airspace in addition to existing combat-related activities in airspace closed to civil traffic. The wide variance of types and characteristics, from hobbyist quadcopters to high-altitude large jet aircraft encompassing broadly varying levels of range and autonomy, continues to create new opportunities for both nations and non-state actors⁹.

Is there controversy?

However, military uses of UAS are often perceived to be ethically challenging. The specific ethical concerns levied vary based on role and payload (bombs vs cameras, for example) and degrees of autonomy (controlled in real time vs onboard Artificial Intelligence (AI)). Current systems tend to be unitary and flown remotely by human operators, whilst future systems are predicted to include increasingly autonomous systems able to operate cooperatively without real-time human input – leading to the potential for 'swarms' to achieve objectives over large areas, including overwhelming

⁷ UK MOD *JDP 0-30.2* (2017)

⁸ Gambold (2011); RAF (2020)

⁹ Clover and Feng (2017)

enemy air defences. These concerns are likely to be exacerbated by a continuing lack of public understanding about existing legal and operational constraints on the use of force. Aside from the ethical arguments about the use of force, future capabilities will embody broader popular concerns about the growth of AI capability in general. In a civil context the ethics of drones relates to the moral principles of how to use them within civil society and the moral hazards that might arise from risks they pose. This will give rise to regulatory and legal challenges that need to be addressed for the future force to leverage UAS capability flexibly at home and overseas, in addition to affecting the broader development of these vehicles and their systems. This dissertation will begin by exploring risks associated with procurement and employment of UAS from an ethical and perceptual perspective, before considering strategies to reduce these.

What about practical challenges?

But UAS are not merely constrained by perceptual and ethical challenges. The novel and networked nature of complex systems supporting the operation of UA and the exploitation of the data they collect, also creates threats to their successful operation. Cross-domain vulnerabilities borne of their reliance on the space and cyber domains are scalable (the lower the autonomy the higher the liability) which is usually the inverse of their vulnerability to ethical arguments. Balancing these competing vulnerabilities will be complex and contingent on an accurate assessment of the relative risk of external factors, such as whether the ability of an adversary to degrade contingent infrastructure exceeds the risk of a loss of public support for a given operation. Threats through the space and cyber domains can degrade or deny UAS to an extent greater than that for legacy platforms. It is not clear that this such cross-domain vulnerabilities explicitly or cohesively considered in balancing procurement for a future force, at least insofar as such decisions are available in the public domain. Therefore, this dissertation will also explore the vulnerability of current and future UAS to cross-domain threats from Space and Cyber, the likely efficacy of potential mitigation and consequential lessons for creating a balanced future force.

What does this paper offer?

This dissertation surveys ethical and practical issues that create liabilities, as well as advantages for UAS in the UK's future force. It will review existing evidence to situate the relative viability of UAS in the UK's future force, with reference to those ethical and practical risks. The paper will support a conclusion that perceptual and ethical challenges to existing military RPAS are diminishing, but increased autonomy will amplify public concerns surrounding future UA. The success of regulatory and legal integration of UA within civil airspace will influence public acceptance, capability, and costs. Ethical issues and public perception are surveyed from the point of view of their influence on military force decisions and the effect of commercial procurement on the pace of research and technology. This paper will also explore the cross-domain liabilities inherent with UA capabilities and the extent to which this differs from inhabited aircraft. This paper will conclude that such vulnerabilities are influenced by the level of autonomy. To influence the public debate and ensure the technical capability of future UA can be fully harnessed, a novel normative framework for autonomous decision making is needed. More widely, the critical cross-domain contingencies for mission success that UA share with inhabited aircraft, render the requirement for novel command and control arrangements, to coordinate activity in the space and cyber domains more closely with existing operational structures.

The Civil Integration of UA: Drones at Home

Within democratic societies, the public perception of UAS will affect their integration into civil airspace and underline the economic and political argument for their prevalence in a future force. Furthermore, the extent to which UA are integrated into civil airspace and thus exploited for commercial purposes will indirectly affect procurement costs for the future force, by influencing the pace and scale of research and development.

When considering the ethics and moral principles relating to UAS, the first challenge is discriminating between the plethora of purposes, sizes, payloads, operators, and degrees of autonomy. Fundamentally each of these affects ethical outcomes and hazards. This section will look at the applied ethics affecting the integration of UA into civil society and how this might transpose into considerations for those planning a future force. More specifically, it will consider the ethical and legal constraints that UAS will be subject to when operating outside a combat environment.

Individual and societal impact

On an individual level, even the smallest UA may cause injury if it collides with a person¹⁰. The more calamitous RTL potentially caused by damage to larger commercial aircraft on approach or departure is already well recognised, with management attempts such as geofencing (programming preventing inadvertent operation in a sensitive area) in place to reduce likelihood¹¹. Putting injury and damage aside, there is also the ethical impact of intentional or unintentional interference with economic and social outcomes in society – the closure of Gatwick Airport between 19-21 December 2018 due to fears of a quadcopter incursion is estimated to have affected 82,000 passengers and resulted in direct costs of £50m¹². The measures taken to balance the freedom to operate UA with potential ethical impacts will directly and indirectly affect the attraction of UAS in UK future force design. The direct impact is to constrain or permit the use of military UA within civil airspace, but the indirect effect on the prevalence and perception of UA in civil society is probably more powerful in second order effects.

There are concerns on a societal level too. The effect of increasing automation in many industries will affect employment opportunities by changing the skills and knowledge demanded by employers. In the case of UA, demand for engineers (especially software experts) is likely to increase as demand for traditional pilot skills diminish. The extent to which this transition is managed and reflected in the education process may have a practical effect on the employment pool available for UK Defence. Given that recruitment and retention is currently a major concern for the MOD, this may warrant strategic consideration when assessing the future force structure.

Distinction between civil and conflict ethical concerns

Headlines about killer robots often suggest the ethical debate about the use of military UA is limited to the use of force in an international context¹³. However, research suggests that a plethora of ethical constructs apply to UA in a domestic sense, across both the military and civilian spectrum. In one 2016 systematic review into the civil use of drones in domestic airspace, the two most

¹⁰ [BBC News \(2014\)](#); [Weil \(2013\)](#)

¹¹ [UK CAA Safety Notice-2020/002 \(2020\)](#); [UK Parliament Science and technology Committee \(2019\)](#)

¹² [Calder \(2019\)](#)

¹³ [Slaughterbots \(2017\)](#); [Drone Wars UK \(2020\)](#); [Sabbagh \(2019\)](#)

frequently cited concerns were safety of flight and inadequate legal regulation¹⁴. Additional concerns included privacy, airspace access, information integrity and commercial factors. As certifiable UA proliferate, integration of military UA into shared environments will require consideration of these issues.

Why are civil ethics important to UAS in the military future force?

Understanding UA integration into civilian airspace is important for their role in future force design for several reasons. Firstly, the freedom to operate aircraft in unsegregated airspace increases the value of existing UA by allowing them to flexibly fulfil their role anywhere in the world. This speaks to some of the attributes that are doctrinally sacrosanct for air forces, including agility and ubiquity¹⁵. In the UK for example, the armed forces currently operate a mix of inhabited and uninhabited Intelligence Surveillance Target Acquisition and Reconnaissance (ISTAR) aircraft. The largest of these in UK service is the *Reaper* (also used for combat including Close Air Support (CAS)), with a 70ft wingspan and a maximum altitude of 50,000ft.

UA are often capable of delivering similar or improved capability compared to their inhabited counterparts. *Reaper* for example fulfils a similar capability to *Shadow* – a much heavier inhabited aircraft based on the Beechcraft King-Air. In this example, *Reaper* as an UA delivers much better persistence at lower cost but is limited by regulatory constraints preventing it sharing civil airspace with manned aircraft. To date, UA are almost always limited to flying within segregated airspace or with another mitigation such as an inhabited chase plane. The first steps to proceed beyond this were taken last year.¹⁶ As permissions remain very limited, the requirement for segregated airspace currently constrains the ability of UA to contribute to Defence outputs where such deconfliction is not available. This might be about to change with the advent of larger RPAS built to certifiable standards, perhaps with integral ‘Detect And Avoid’ (DAA) capabilities.¹⁷ DAA systems are designed to both identify aircraft that pose a collision risk and allow UA to take avoiding action autonomously when an otherwise remotely piloted aircraft loses connectivity with its crew.¹⁸ Interestingly, most press releases emphasise improved situational awareness (SA) for the remote crew, rather than aircraft behaviour when command link to the remote crew is interrupted (a ‘lost-link’ event). This is likely indicative of a desire to play down the ethical implications of autonomous flight.

Secondly, aside from the economic and practical advantages derived from this flexibility, permission to operate UA in civil airspace is likely to expand the commercial market. A clearly defined regulatory structure with certifiable equipment will encourage innovation and create market opportunities¹⁹. Existing UA provide endurance and cost advantages over inhabited platforms for a host of civil and commercial tasks – for example: cinematography, survey, search and rescue or communications relay. Some studies predict more than 10,000 UA will be in commercial use by 2025.²⁰ Excluding very small recreational UA²¹, this represents 40 percent of all current commercial

¹⁴ Luppicini and So (2016) p111

¹⁵ UK MOD (2017) *JDPO-30*

¹⁶ [Lillain \(2019\)](#)

¹⁷ [UK Govt. \(2020\)](#)

¹⁸ [NASA \(2020\)](#)

¹⁹ De Miguel Molina (2018) p7; p11

²⁰ Yacoub (2020) p2

²¹ [US FAA \(2019\)](#) estimated in 2019 there were 1.32million small recreational UA in the USA

aircraft²² and up to 25percent of all aircraft worldwide²³. Such an expanded market will provide an enhanced industrial base and economies of scale necessary for accelerated development of military UA. This growth is likely to be greatest in North America, Asia and Europe – the regions which host the current market leaders in UA development²⁴. Notably, these regions also host a majority of UK strategic partners and potential peer adversaries.

Thirdly, the prevalence of UA in civil and commercial roles is likely to relieve UA from their vilification as dystopian weapon systems. As UA increasingly take on roles with a positive impact in society, whether in economic, socio-political or practical terms, the more acceptable they will be to the public²⁵. Examples might be the delivery of medicines during COVID-19, or rescue with the Coast Guard.²⁶ The civil and commercial use of UA will help to take the debate beyond the current paradoxical position that UA are, in Western democracies, both a political liability (when perceived as killer robots committing cowardly acts) and a political advantage (facilitating increasingly effective surveillance or strikes, without risk to life to own forces).

The International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) position

The overriding concern about integration of UA into civil airspace is one of safety, but this is underpinned by the economic importance of affording and maintaining provision of existing commercial activity. For this reason, the International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) wrote in 2011 that only remotely piloted aircraft (RPA) will be allowed to integrate into unsegregated airspace in the foreseeable future, with integrated autonomy being considerably further off²⁷. This seems to be borne out of an interpretation in Article 8 from the Chicago Convention (ratified in 1947), and based on the assertion that: in order for an UA to be ‘so controlled as to obviate a danger to civil aircraft’, and apply an equivalence to ‘due regard’, there must be a licenced, remote pilot.²⁸ Unfortunately, this creates a paradox which ignores the requirement for UA to resolve their own potential airspace conflicts if the real-time command link with their remote pilot is inhibited. Consequently, given that regulation is ultimately down to signatory states, this assumption is likely to be challenged as DAA systems are procured. The requirement to regulate and certify existing automation, including instrument landing systems (CAT IIIc allowing for no pilot input until after touchdown) and automatic collision avoidance (TCAS II requiring compliance with automatic instructions in primacy to the situational awareness of pilots or air traffic control) demonstrates an existing recognition that algorithmic processing has a proven safety case. Levels of autonomy and a hierarchy for algorithmic processing and machine learning will be explored later in this paper.

Integration principles

The current approach to integrating UA into the existing Air Traffic Management (ATM) constructs assume that UA should mirror procedures and behave as inhabited aircraft might²⁹. This reflects the wider psychological principle that humans are more willing to relate to robotic activity when actions

²² Airbus, as cited by Topham (2019)

²³ Airliners.net

²⁴ Tractica (2017), as cited by De Miguel Molina (2018) p10

²⁵ De Miguel Molina (2018) p10

²⁶ [University of Southampton \(2020\)](#); [Elbit Systems \(2020\)](#)

²⁷ [ICAO Cir 328 AN/190 \(2011\)](#)

²⁸ [ICAO Cir 328 AN/190 \(2011\)](#)

²⁹ [Dubot \(201\)2 p14](#); [Killeen \(2013\) p16](#)

and intentions are predictable³⁰. By operating within controlled airspace where a minimum level of electronic conspicuity and compliance is assured, it is easier to create cooperative avoidance protocols than if, say, an UA was operating in uncontrolled airspace in the vicinity of a non-transponding hang glider. Controlled airspace tends to be congested areas set aside to minimise risk to commercial aircraft operations – primarily airlines. The DAA approach for controlled airspace is therefore less technically complex than that for uncontrolled airspace, since aircraft operating under instrument flight rules are more predictable and easier to detect, but it also requires the most robust level of assurance, especially in the case of lost-link events. This approach is achievable and perhaps desirable for UA with similar characteristics to existing controlled airspace users but does not address many of the commercial applications which require short-distance, low-altitude provision. The pace of change has been slower than many proponents predicted, and uncertainties remain about the provision and accreditation of suitably autonomous DAA systems³¹. Looking beyond DAA systems specifically, it remains to be seen how regulatory approaches may differ between regions. For example, although the next UK combat RPAS *Protector* has been designed to meet NATO standardisation and US Federal Aviation Authority (FAA) certification, it is uncertain if there will be additional assurance issues with the UK Civil Aviation Authority (CAA). Integration on a national and international basis is clearly a key liability for UA in the future force, and one which must be a priority.

Commercial / Airspace prioritisation

Stepping down from the integration of large UA into controlled airspace, a major commercial interest is in low-altitude and slow speed quadcopters (often employed as a misnomer to include small UA with more than four rotors). One such use case is the “last mile” delivery of logistics chains. Amazon for example is actively researching UA deliveries, including a beta test of a service advertised as ‘Amazon Prime Air’³². Whilst the characteristics of the UA used in trials neither require nor benefit from access to controlled airspace, it is unclear how broader deconfliction from other airspace users might be achieved. Inhabited military aircraft sometimes fly low-level (below 400’, which is the ceiling for the UA in the trial) but could not ‘see and avoid’ the UA currently in use – as required by regulation in uncontrolled, Class G airspace. The risk to crews coming into conflict is therefore evident. Civil aircraft are regulated to remain greater than 500’ from persons or objects, except when landing or taking off, but many smaller airfields are not easily identifiable or registered which could lead to conflict with inhabited civil traffic too.³³ Future solutions will represent both a boon for UA in future force design (by creating permissive logistical opportunities and enlarging the market for UA), and a hinderance if it provides a congested layer of airspace close to the ground.

Privacy / Information integrity

Another of the key popular concerns about UA is that their association with a lack of personal privacy. This is most evident in community reactions to the sorts of small UA that are often used in communities by hobbyists or small-businesses such as photo- or videographers³⁴. The discourse surrounding military RPAS being intelligence and surveillance assets (whilst helpful to balance

³⁰ [Williams \(2018\) p72](#)

³¹ [Killeen \(2013\) p18](#); CAP722

³² <https://www.amazon.com/Amazon-Prime-Air/>

³³ [UK CAA CAP393 \(2019\)](#)

³⁴ [McLaughlin \(2019\)](#)

negative connotations with any weapons capability) also contributes to this perception, as does the emphasis on surveillance for platforms with search and rescue³⁵. This perceptual challenge is exacerbated by the media and in popular entertainment³⁶. In law, the privacy challenge is already addressed in part by existing protocols, for example the EU General Data Protection Regulations and national legislation limiting state surveillance³⁷. However, the perception of “nosy neighbours” and intrusive state surveillance is a highly emotive one for many people and community groups. The scale of this challenge therefore will vary for commercial enterprise, military, and private operators, but it is the commercial influence which is most likely to influence public perception to change. Fortuitously, within a market-driven society, advertising and sales is second nature to most firms.

Until this wider change in perception is achieved, military UA in the future force may need to have the capability to operate discreetly until the use of UAs for community tasks such as ambulatory care, transport or police support have substantially changed public perceptions. For surveillance or monitoring, this would suggest an emphasis in the near-term future force on quiet UA operating at a range and altitude to render them largely unnoticeable to those on the ground. This requirement is already evident in their role overseas, with crews routinely trained to operate in this way. At home, this would usually place them in controlled airspace which speaks to the requirement for certifiable and cooperative systems. In the meantime, public interest groups opposed to state surveillance will continue to apply pressure for legislative and ethical standards³⁸. Certain activities including interception of communications and extended surveillance of large areas are likely to continue to be constrained by existing legislation limiting domestic intelligence programmes, so a modular approach to UA payloads in the future force will be desirable.³⁹.

³⁵ [The Maritime Executive \(2020\)](#)

³⁶ “Eye in the Sky” (2015); “A Good Kill” (2014).

³⁷ De Miguel Molina (2019) p78

³⁸ Electronic Frontier Foundation - <https://www.eff.org/issues/surveillance-drones>

³⁹ In the UK, the Intelligence Services Act, Human Rights Act and the Regulation of Investigatory Powers Act.

Warfighting: The ‘Distance Paradox’⁴⁰

Integration of UA into civil airspace will have a major impact on the flexibility of UA in the future force, but there remains concern about the ethical implications of using UA to take warfighting actions. There is a considerable amount of academic interest on this subject, but the international and domestic media the narrative has sometimes been diminished to the idea of ‘robotic killer drones’.⁴¹ Current levels of automation do not support that interpretation. Instead, RPAS rely on certified crews often located away from the battlefield, with few forward deployed. This presents a ‘distance paradox’, the fundamental question of which is whether the incidence of conflict or the likelihood of civilian casualties and damage to property is exacerbated by the crew being away from the battlefield.⁴² This would affect the *jus in bello* concept of legal action in war. This section of the paper will explore the case for this argument as it relates to existing RPAS. The next section will consider how any ‘distance paradox’ may change as higher levels of autonomy become technologically possible and operationally desirable in UAS.

*Remote Intimacy*⁴³ - *psychological harms*

The idea that RPAS crews have degraded situational awareness and vision has been discounted⁴⁴. Yet there remains a commonly held view that operating remotely piloted aircraft may create a sense of detachment that would increase the propensity for lethal engagements, with concomitant increases in damage to property and, perhaps, civilian casualties⁴⁵. This is often presented as being self-evident, and regularly accompanied by glib remarks about a “PlayStation generation” or “PlayStation mentality”⁴⁶. Instead, evidence to the contrary is building. Several first-hand commentators and independent researchers have provided qualitative evidence for high fidelity imagery creating psychological proximity⁴⁷. Indeed, this high-fidelity imagery, provided for the sorts of long-duration flights attributable to UA endurance, allows UAS to generate a more comprehensive “pattern of life” (POL) providing better intelligence for engagement decisions than might otherwise be possible. Some operational activity involves weeks or months of near continual surveillance, something simply not possible with legacy platforms, which affords a unique ability to make judgements about the best time for any attack to ensure the correct target is hit with minimum risk to civilians and non-combatant property. Furthermore, the highly networked nature of UAS allows for improved communications and decision making, also reducing the likelihood of miscalculations and thereby risk of collateral damage or loss of civilian life. The environment for crews operating RPAS from within a Ground Control Station (GCS) is usually like an inhabited cockpit, especially in terms of equipment and crew interaction.⁴⁸ Any association with computer games is further undermined by the training pathways for such crews, which frequently includes certification in inhabited aircraft and years of professional training⁴⁹.

⁴⁰ Lee (2018)

⁴¹ [McKelvey \(2012\)](#)

⁴² Lee (2018b) p106; Enemark (2013) p327

⁴³ Gusterson (2016) p59

⁴⁴ Killeen (2013) p23; Lee (2018); Lee (2018b) p7

⁴⁵ Cole *et al* (2010) as cited in Lee(2018) p3; Olsthoorn (2011) p126; Singer (2009) p332

⁴⁶ Cole *et al* (2010)

⁴⁷ Martin and Sasser (2010) p55; Lee (2018); Cole (2017)

⁴⁸ [GA ASI \(2020\)](#); [Ramos \(2016\)](#); [Hobbs and Lyall \(2015\)](#)

⁴⁹ Hansard PQ 26 Jul 16; [Duray \(2019\) p5](#)

There is also evidence for, in the UK at least, an organisational culture which emphasises ‘something akin to obsession with zero civcas’.⁵⁰ Such an approach would be consistent with restrictive rules of engagement (ROE) and go beyond the stipulations of the Law of Armed Conflict (LOAC); which simply requires that civilians be distinguished from the enemy wherever possible, and not deliberately targeted⁵¹. Whilst any military action must be necessary and proportionate to its aims, an organisational culture obsessed on achieving ‘zero civcas’ is also consistent with attempts to mitigate increased incidence of post-traumatic stress amongst armed RPAS crews, which evidence suggests is exacerbated by exposure to unplanned events.⁵² Further evidence for the increased incidence of broader moral and psychological injury, attributable to visually disturbing imagery, is continuing to build.⁵³

Chivalry – an unfair fight?

Although increasingly contentious, the idea that the crews of present-day RPAS are unharmed by their operations persists. Putting to one side the argument (which evidence increasingly suggests is specious) that their physical detachment makes them more likely to use lethal force, some critics argue use of UA is unfair or disproportionate given the enemy cannot immediately threaten them. Unfortunately for those that use this argument, the idea that striking an enemy without reciprocal vulnerability is unethical has consistently proven impractically idealistic throughout history.⁵⁴ Asynchronous conflict is unavoidable, with each adversary seeking to gain novel advantage over the other. There is no appreciable increased risk to the pilot of an inhabited aircraft (operating at representative operational altitudes) than that of an UA, at least in the sorts of permissive airspace where currently fielded UA are routinely employed, such as recent conflicts in Afghanistan, Iraq and Syria.

In at least one way, RPAS crews are credibly at increased physical risk compared to those piloting inhabited aircraft – namely targeted ‘lone wolf’ attacks in their domestic environment, which is a known jihadist objective. RPAS crew basing is open source knowledge and until recently the bespoke badging for RPAS crews rendered them easily identifiable⁵⁵. Recent organisational change within the RAF to no longer distinguish (in terms of uniform, medallic recognition, remuneration and conditions of service) is not merely a security measure, but provides a powerful indication that the Service no longer considers its RPAS crews to be any different to other combatant pilots⁵⁶.

Aside from the ability of enemy combatants to threaten UA crews directly, reciprocity can also be demonstrated in the increasingly ubiquitous availability of UAS capability. UAS are now widely employed by nation states worldwide, across all continents. At least 95 countries now operate

⁵⁰ Lee (2018) p4

⁵¹ International Humanitarian Law

⁵² Gusterson (2016) p8; Chappelle (2014); Chappelle (2019)

⁵³ Lee (2018b) pp113-131; Simmons 2018, Hurrell *et al* (2018), Donnelly *et al* (2015), Mumford *et al* (2015), Perez *et al* (2010) as cited by Lee and Kara Giannopoulos (2019)

⁵⁴ Lee (2020) p2

⁵⁵ Lawson (2013)

⁵⁶ [AFPRB 49th Report \(2020\)](#); [Royal Air Force on Twitter \(2019\)](#); [BBC News \(2019\)](#)

military drone programmes⁵⁷. Non-state actors including insurgent groups are also generating capability - Daesh have demonstrated the ability to use UA for attack, ISTAR and logistic purposes⁵⁸.

Do UAS reduce the threshold for lethal action?

Psychological and domestic security concerns aside, the physical risk to life for UAS operators is lower than inhabited aircraft for a given sortie. Thus, they are attractive to international leaders weighing options below the threshold for full conflict. This leads to one of the most frequent criticisms of UA - namely the perception that they increase the likelihood of armed conflict and potentially thereby impact *jus ad bellum*. Whilst this is a valid concern, it is not unique to UA and is more reflective of new capabilities in general. The argument that UA have this effect has parallels in the well-understood attraction of air power as a military option when monetary costs or loss of life are key considerations. No new realisation, this is reminiscent of the earliest air power theorists and evidenced throughout recent history – for example by the newly-founded RAF in policing the British Empire, the use of mass bombing in the Second World War and the employment of the Op LINEBACKER raids in Vietnam.

Looking for specific evidence that UA reduce the threshold required for conflict is harder to find, but there may be indications as far back as 1999, in conclusions drawn by the USAF as to the rapidity with which politicians sought to use air power as the key lever of military threat⁵⁹. The subsequent use of a *Predator* UA in the Balkans created an association between UA and independent use of the air domain. More recently, there is evidence in the approach of the White House to authorisation of operations in Libya in 2011, with attempts to circumvent congressional authority⁶⁰. However, whilst UA were a far larger component in 2011, it is more likely to be the tenets attributable to air platforms (according to JDP 0-30: height, speed, reach, agility and ubiquity) that are most attractive rather than simply the RtL. This rather undermines the argument that *jus ad bellum* is affected simply by aircraft being uninhabited although there is ample evidence it is seen as a political expediency.

It remains interesting that the perceived ethical and moral disadvantages of UA appear to be reflected in a continued emphasis on using inhabited aircraft.⁶¹ For example, UK *Reaper* has, in recent years, employed the same proportion of munitions as similarly employed fast jet aircraft during Op SHADER, yet public messaging emphasises RPAS' role in surveillance rather than their role in strike. UA have been demonstrated to deliver munitions in less than an eighth of the time necessary for a traditional fighter to employ a proportionally similar effect⁶². When employing low-yield munitions, this allows for engagement in a wider range of locations and circumstances (tighter windows of opportunity, especially when targeting moving vehicles) which might otherwise present concern about civilian casualties or unreasonable damage to property. This reticence to fully acknowledge the capability of UA involvement in operations might be explained by a desire to manage public perception, but it is also evident within the Services given a prevailing operational

⁵⁷ [Gettinger \(2020\)](#)

⁵⁸ Bunker (2015) p15, p18

⁵⁹ as cited in Mahnken (2008) p187

⁶⁰ Enemark (2013) p329

⁶¹ Duray (2019) p14

⁶² Duray (2019) p14, citing a strafing run vs hellfire missile.

tendency to favour inhabited platforms for attack if they are available⁶³. This perceptual bias amongst practitioners needs to be overcome for UA to have their value maximised in the future force.

In the case of the public narrative, a reduction in emphasis on the role of UA might suggest they are less likely to lead to escalation due to both a reduced RtL and their continued obscurity within the public narrative. If this hypothesis is correct, then whilst the threshold for employment of UAS may be lower, escalation is less likely. On the other hand, countering activity by UA is complex and the ambiguity surrounding thresholds may lead to unintentional escalation⁶⁴, so any political calculations on the risk of using UA must consider the exacerbating risk of an adversary miscalculating the escalatory impact of targeting an UA. The defining characteristic is one of uncertainty, but as UAS become more prevalent the opportunity for a perceptual air-gap between their use and the threshold for retaliation will diminish. In the longer term, the distinction between inhabited and uninhabited aircraft is expected to diminish as a cultural phenomenon both inside operators' organisation and in wider society, as personnel become more experienced in UA capabilities. This will render this less of an issue for the future force than the present one.

⁶³ Duray (2019) p14

⁶⁴ Dyndal (2013) p112

Future Challenges: The Autonomy Paradigm

Defining autonomy

The rapid pace of technological change suggests that future UA will have increased levels of automation, autonomy, and AI. In China this is a primary aim of their UAS development and the exploitation of AI is recognised as strategically important not only in a Defence context but as a means of global leadership.⁶⁵ This presents another semantic challenge, to draw a distinction between terms variously used to describe degrees of operation without human input. There is no commonly agreed taxonomy, despite early attempts to elucidate a hierarchy of independence and attach levels of autonomy within a Defence context⁶⁶. Confusingly, these terms are often used to mean different things, especially across various academic disciplines and in various operational contexts.

For the purposes of this paper, automation or automatic describes a pre-programmed activity such as a three-dimensional route follow. This is the case for military RPAS currently known to be in operational use. Autonomy requires more capabilities. It suggests an ability to cater for the unexpected – for example, the ability for an UA to choose between tasks and outcomes based on a contextualised, on-board situational awareness. This would be recognised by an ethicist as decisional autonomy – as the UA is not capable of making its own objectives, rather it chooses courses of action to achieve them within laws provided by an external (human) agent⁶⁷. AI is a very ambiguously used term, but it is generally understood to represent a much more comprehensive collection of capabilities, including internal machine learning, that enable the AI to behave in ways not explicitly foreseen by the programmers.

Future AI will still have limitations based on human constraints placed on software-derived autonomous behaviour, system hardware limitations and aerodynamic design. These will reflect regulatory and legal constraints, but there will remain a requirement for ethical system design, including a need to reduce unintentional human bias in algorithms⁶⁸. Some theorists have expressed concerns about future AI having independent will, consciousness, or an ability to choose its own objectives. This level of sentience and sapience is undesirable, but unlikely. Even if it is designed, it is unlikely to be procured for a military purpose - disobedience is generally undesirable in the military. However, lower levels of autonomy (which nonetheless go far further than existing automation) are likely to be critical to military advantage. An ability to categorise and manage the integration of these capabilities into operational command and control structures is key to maximising their benefit whilst preserving, where necessary, the ‘human-in-the-loop’ (a key element of current UK policy).⁶⁹

Law and morality

For UA in the future force to exhibit autonomy beyond pre-programmed routes and uncontextualised behaviour, the UA itself must be able to choose between courses of action which

⁶⁵ Zheng (2018 as cited in Allen (2019) p5-6; [Allen \(2019\)](#) p3-4

⁶⁶ [Scholes \(2002\)](#); [US DOD as cited in Killeen \(2013\)](#) [Massie \(2016b\)](#)

Birmingham Policy Commission (2013), William and McNail (2013) as cited in Lee (2020) p8

⁶⁷ [Gros et al \(2012\)](#) p7-12

⁶⁸ Lee (2020) p8

⁶⁹ UK Parliament (2013) col.733, as cited in Lee (2020) p6

may present ethical conundrums⁷⁰. This “applied trolley problem” is the common challenge posed to other autonomous vehicles, including the development of self-driving cars⁷¹. The legal framework for such vehicles is actively under discussion, including multidisciplinary teams seeking to reform existing national legislation⁷². Existing military RPAS circumvent this requirement by holding the human pilot responsible for flight safety and operational activity both when the aircraft is under their control and by pre-programming a suitably low risk alternative if direct control is lost. They follow identical ROE and decision-making processes for identifying and engaging targets to that of inhabited aircraft⁷³. The limited automation of existing military RPAS allows this ‘slave morality’, reflecting an extension of the legal principle that “he who acts through another does the act himself”⁷⁴. Smaller UA in the civilian market behave similarly except often the behaviour is pre-programmed by the manufacturer – such as a straightforward local landing or recovery along a defined pathway. If an incident were to occur an alternative legal accountability could be incurred, namely negligence if the design or decision to operate the aircraft was deemed unsafe⁷⁵. However, these two methods of legal accountability become increasingly tenuous as the complexity of programming and ability for UA to exhibit independent behaviour, by deciding between courses of action, increases.

Therefore, the concept of autonomous behaviour in UA urgently requires a new normative framework of legal and ethical principles agreed internationally. Attempts to achieve this would appear to be especially urgent given that the practical potential for autonomous engagements is already evident in limited circumstances. Theoretically, air-to-air engagements beyond visual range are given as one such example.⁷⁶ Limited trials have already been carried out in arming existing RPAS for air-to-air engagements.⁷⁷ Yet the potential for autonomous advantage is not limited to long-range ‘shoot and scoot’ tactics. Autonomy allows for actions that could not be facilitated by a remote pilot, including close-in high-energy “dogfighting” manoeuvres that would cause antennae to lose connection with the communications relay, resulting in a loss of link with a remote crew. Such a framework would be a strategic advantage to nations, such as the UK, that want to incorporate UA as part of a future force that operates within a rules-based international system, or systems⁷⁸. A failure to do so will be reminiscent of the failure to agree *Rules for Aerial Warfare* at the Hague in 1922⁷⁹, which, if adhered to, had potential to limit the devastating effects of strategic bombing of cities, such as that conducted by Bomber Command during the Second World War.

‘Article 43.3. Any bombardment of cities, towns, villages, habitations and buildings which are not situated in the immediate vicinity of the operations of land forces, is forbidden.’⁸⁰

Commission of Jurists, 1922

⁷⁰ [Gros et al \(2012\) p7-12](#)

⁷¹ [Nyholm and Sids \(2016\)](#)

⁷² [Zheng \(2015\)](#)

⁷³ Shannon (2015) as cited in Lee (2020) p3

⁷⁴ [Gros et al \(2012\) p7-12](#)

⁷⁵ [Gros et al \(2012\) p7-12](#)

⁷⁶ [Killeen \(2013\) p12](#)

⁷⁷ [Whittle \(2011\) p30](#); [Allison \(2018\)](#)

⁷⁸ Field (2018); Chalmers (2019)

⁷⁹ Lee (2020) p2

⁸⁰ As cited in Lee (2020)p2

Whilst UN efforts to incorporate a ban on lethal autonomous robots appear to attract majority support from the public worldwide, efforts are currently frustrated by several nations including Russia, the United States, South Korea, Israel and Australia.⁸¹ This is likely to be attributable to a lack of agreement about how to define prohibited capabilities. There is evidence that some nations, such as China, publicly support such a ban but seek such a narrow definition on the prohibited article as to make an agreement nugatory.⁸² Most nations have differing policy positions, exacerbated by a lack of clarity over definitions and how they relate to practical design.⁸³ Desirable or otherwise, continuing international proliferation of such capabilities gives rise to a UK requirement for such automation to be leveraged within the future force.

The Value of Autonomy

In a civil context, autonomy may help to ensure regulatory compliance by removing human error. A case in point might be the prospect for ‘drone intelligence’ to prevent incursions into restricted airspace such as that which caused the Gatwick Airport shutdown in 2018.⁸⁴ In a commercial sense, the use of autonomous UA deliveries will create economic advantage. In fact, any set of circumstances where rapid processing and algorithmic decision-making is desirable would be improved by greater autonomy. In doctrinal terms within the military, this is reflected in the desire to act quickly and interrupt the enemy observe-orient-decide-act (OODA) loop.⁸⁵ It should also be recognised that some examples of autonomy in military systems have been around for decades – such as the defensive aids suites designed to nullify the threat of incoming missiles⁸⁶, or the autonomous targeting capabilities of missiles such as Brimstone.⁸⁷

Cooperative dispensability

By way of case-study, one of the key future capabilities in development relates to the ability for UA to exhibit autonomy by cooperatively communicating independent of larger networks and ground-control infrastructure. Some aspects of cooperation are already proven – such as the ability of a salvo of “fire and forget” missiles to use algorithms to avoid all hitting the same target⁸⁸. An early swarming technique was used by Israel as part of the 1973 Yom Kippur War and in 1982 in the Syrian Bekaa Valley to suppress air defences.⁸⁹ These swarm tactics will be enhanced by the ability of simpler, expendable UA to cooperate rapidly, without human input. Intel (the microprocessor manufacturer) has already demonstrated a swarm of 1,218 drones, but this appears to have relied on programmed behaviours rather than inter-drone communication.⁹⁰ More recently, in 2016, the US Defence Department dropped 103 Perdix drones from a legacy fighter jet, displaying collective decision making, adaptive formation flight and self-healing.⁹¹

⁸¹ [Delcker \(2019\)](#); [Gill \(2018\)](#)

⁸² Allen (2019) p7

⁸³ [Stauffer \(2020\)](#)

⁸⁴ [Turniansky \(2019\)](#)

⁸⁵ [Alberts and Hayes \(2003\)](#)

⁸⁶ [Killeen \(2013\) p3](#)

⁸⁷ [MBDA \(2015\)](#)

⁸⁸ [Brimstone Salvo Firing - Video](#)

⁸⁹ Killeen (2013) p

⁹⁰ [Kallenborn \(2018\)](#)

⁹¹ [Gimber \(2019\)](#)

Britain's swarming programmes are said to be 'exceeding expectations', with the RAF assigning 216 Squadron in 2019 to develop this as an operational option 'within a year'.⁹² This activity is likely to fall significantly below the level of 'full autonomy' and such a capability is expected to be included within the future force given the allocation of a specific Squadron to the task. Both the swarming concept and the 'loyal wingman', under development by the Rapid Capability Office's Project-MOSQUITO⁹³, rely upon the concept of sacrificing dispensable assets, to overwhelm an enemy threat. Whilst this was also postulated as an advantage for RPA such as *Predator* and *Reaper* during their development, the UK force is sufficiently lean as to render this impractical. It seems likely therefore that the future force will contain both sacrificial and protected UA based on cost.

Limitations of autonomous decision making

In 2018, the US Department of Defence published a request to fund research into 'Automatic Target Recognition of Personnel and Vehicles from an Unmanned Aerial System Using Learning Algorithms'⁹⁴. This builds upon the ability of existing fire and forget weapon systems such as the Brimstone missile. In Brimstone's case, it can select the most valuable targets based on comparisons of vehicle shape based on millimetric wave sensing. It was originally envisaged for defending against armoured regiments in the Cold War. However, an ability to discriminate between combatants and non-combatants in a shared environment is likely to be much more challenging. The technical challenge is compounded by a reluctance in the technology industry to engage with Defence research of this kind – as indicated by the petition of 3000 Google staff to withdraw from the associated technology of Project MAVEN⁹⁵. Indeed, the ability for truly autonomous tactical decisions will often involve taking subjective decisions such as the 'least bad option'.

'The system should implement learning algorithms that provide operational flexibility by allowing the target set and DRCI taxonomy to be quickly adjusted and to operate in different environments'⁹⁶.

US Department of Defense

Machine learning for relative risk is an existing cross-disciplinary area of study.⁹⁷ As Paltrinieri *et al* observe, risk is a dynamically evolving assessment in dynamic environments. In addition, the data on which risk can be assessed may not be available in a timely or accessible manner. For example, knowledge about whether an aircraft has been observed when choosing a reduced altitude may only become available to intelligence analysts over time, by another means. In examples like this, a positive-feedback loop is not available to allow for machine learning during operations.

A more critical example is the need to discriminate on the basis of proportionality, especially during defensive engagements – or how to cope with highly ambiguous contextualised circumstances (such as judging the age of combatants and assessing the correct course of action when presented with child soldiers). There is evidence that the multi-crew environment of existing RPAS prevents

⁹² [Allison \(2020\)](#); [Mordaunt \(2019\)](#)

⁹³ [Jennings \(2019\)](#)

⁹⁴ As cited in Lee (2020)p4

⁹⁵ BBC News (2018), Wakabayashi and Shane (2018) as cited by Lee (2020) p5; [Cummings \(2019\)](#); [Pellerin \(2017\)](#)

⁹⁶ Lee (2020) p5

⁹⁷ [Paltrinieri et al \(2019\)](#)

accidental loss of life in such circumstances⁹⁸. It might be presumed that there will be some threshold for automatic target recognition that will allow a human to be brought into the loop if ambiguity is detected, but this creates the paradox that the human must have the skill, situational awareness and capability needed to decide on behalf of the machine – perhaps negating the systemic benefits of autonomy in the first place⁹⁹.

Optionally manned – the worst of both worlds?

Prima facie, it might seem that the UK policy for the next generation of fighter aircraft - *Tempest* - be 'optionally manned' is sensible, but further analysis raises concerns. At an organisational level this suggests a requirement to invest in training and maintaining a workforce to fulfil traditional aircrew functions, undermining the economic benefits of autonomy. The aircraft could not be remotely flown, because the RPAS command links are expected to be interrupted during a contested fight with a peer or near-peer adversary. Yet to fly with a human occupant, *Tempest* would be heavier, limited by human physiology and constrained by a need to minimise risk to the pilot. All of these are disadvantages in a fight for control of the air, where autonomy would bring decisive advantage in maximising manoeuvrability and rapid decision making. From an economic perspective, for the aircraft to be inhabited it would need to be designed with life-support systems at additional cost and weight. This could render it unaffordable and have major implications for national industrial outcomes¹⁰⁰.

The effect on organisational culture on the take up of autonomy

Autonomy is clearly a compelling feature for combatants seeking to gain the upper hand. The extent to which autonomy can be harnessed effectively will be influenced by organisational culture and the extent to which delegated decisions are defined and communicated. In theory, on a human level, this happens already. *Mission Command* is a central component of leadership training. Commissioned Officers in initial training and at staff college are exhorted to define the objectives and limitations of a given task rather than the methods of execution. Yet in practice this is often remarked upon as a frustrating antithesis of reality. RPA crews are particularly subject to the "long screwdriver" of senior leadership micromanaging their actions¹⁰¹. The degree to which automation can be trusted will depend on organisational culture as much as combatant commanders' understanding of capability and safeguards. A framework proposed by Wg Cdr Andy Massie in 2016, for understanding the environment surrounding autonomy, might be a key foundational step. He goes on to discuss how to leverage this to introduce autonomy as part of the US Department of Defence 'third-offset strategy' for competitive advantage¹⁰². Whilst this is not directly a component of UK policy, the desire to take advantage of industrial capability in autonomy and AI is expected to influence the current Integrated Review¹⁰³. In turn, this may create an imperative to embrace it within the future force to the extent that international agreements permit.

The imperative for UK policy change

⁹⁸ Lee (2018) pp100-101

⁹⁹ Massie (2016b) p136

¹⁰⁰ [Roblin \(2020\)](#)

¹⁰¹ Duray (2019); Lee (2018)

¹⁰² Massie (2016b); [Hicks \(2017\)](#)

¹⁰³ [Babuta \(2020\)](#)

In 2013, the UK stated its policy on autonomous weapon systems: the operation of automatic weapon systems would always be under human control; and the UK government had no intention of developing full autonomy¹⁰⁴. It might have said much the same about mass bombing raids over major European cities prior to the Second World War. Without a taxonomy of autonomy, it remains difficult to discriminate between levels of processing in political, legal, or ethical discourse. For Britain to take advantage from operating within a rules-based international system, the presence of such a taxonomy of autonomy is essential. It represents a necessary precursor to any international law limiting autonomy in weapon systems. Without such an agreement, history suggests that whatever government intentions may be in peacetime, industry will provide given wartime imperative. Whatever the UK chooses to do, it is clear that other nations may not follow the same course – in 2019 Turkey was reported to be progressing towards using a swarming drone capability, aspiring to become ‘the first nation to use drones able to find, track and kill people without human intervention’¹⁰⁵.

¹⁰⁴ UK Parliament (2013) col.733, as cited in Lee (2020) p6

¹⁰⁵ Hambling (2019) as cited in Lee (2020) p13

Strategies for Ethical and Perceptual Mitigation

The ethics of civil integration, a distance paradox and autonomy require consideration of strategies for mitigation. The success of these strategies is likely to directly influence the extent to which UAS in the future force are constrained by ethical and perceptual liabilities.

Strategy 1 – Communication to diminish conflation of platform with use

There is a central challenge within public discourse. There appears to be a trend amongst critics to conflate the nature of armed UAS with their use by specific agencies. This is understandable given much of the activity has to date been classified and operations are often not in the public domain. However, classifying the processes and procedures represents a strategic error, because it allows for misunderstandings on the part of the wider community to undermine regulatory and procedural changes necessary to use UA most flexibly. In a civil context, this could mean hindering the political imperative for airspace reform. But it is perhaps the public understanding of the military context that continues to lead the public narrative. In recent conflicts, UA have been known to frequently strike individuals (officially hostile combatants, but often termed ‘High Value Individuals’), without a public understanding of the targeting process, operational constraints, or risks realised by not taking such action. Similarly, cases where there are allegedly high levels of civilian casualties speak more about the rules of engagement applicable to the operator than the intrinsic nature of UA. This is clearly understood in the context of UK employment of such systems¹⁰⁶. This conflation is undesirable and deeply flawed, underlining an imperative for better communication and improved transparency as a strategy gaining advantage through UAS in a future force.

For example, heavy use of *Predator* and *Reaper* UA in Afghanistan was predominately conducted by conventional air forces using them for friendly force overwatch, conventional close air support or convoy support¹⁰⁷. Yet it is the relatively infrequent lethal activity by the CIA that is often more newsworthy, with attacks on leadership figures away from the frontlines¹⁰⁸. This contentious activity, derided by critics as extra-judicial killings, is justified by proponents as legitimate self-defence against irregular combatant leadership. To conflate the capability of UAS with these specific use-cases is oversimplistic. Few people would seek to have inhabited fixed wing aircraft banned simply because they were used by the CIA for illegal ‘extraordinary rendition’.¹⁰⁹ Still fewer would advocate doing without the precision, navigation and timing (PNT) capability derived from on-orbit navigational satellites, simply because early rockets were developed for artillery - itself an early form of remote warfare.

Given the demonstrable utility of UAS for wider purposes, a possible strategy to change public perception is to elucidate more clearly their military role, including their involvement with ISTAR, CAS and convoy protection. Tasks such as this are conducted in the same way by existing RPAS as an inhabited aircraft and the effect is the same. The more contentious element of RPAS employment surrounds the legal basis for targeted strikes against combatant individuals. This must be communicated more openly, in such a way as to clearly draw a distinction between the action and the platform used to deliver the effect. Government reluctance to do this may stem in part

¹⁰⁶ [Lee \(2017\), responding to Bandura \(2017\)](#).

¹⁰⁷ Gusterson (2016) p13

¹⁰⁸ Gusterson (2016) p12; Mayer (2009); Radsan (2011) p1202

¹⁰⁹ Singh and Berry (2013)

from the controversy in the USA surrounding the proposed use by the CIA of private military contractors' (PMC) special forces teams to capture or kill Al-Qaeda operatives outside of declared conflict zones¹¹⁰. Human rights lawyers in the US have questioned why the American public countenance such activity with UA given the furore over similar outcomes by special forces – but this could be as much about the role of PMCs or a change in public perception over time¹¹¹. The role of UK RPAS in targeting combatants overseas is well known, so it is now incumbent on the UK government to use transparency to drive the public narrative. Improving public understanding of the process, procedure and limitations will demonstrate that RPAS follow the same procedural approach as inhabited aircraft to lethal action. Future UA with greater autonomy will likely also be subject to an equivalent chain of accountability which could be explained clearly without inhibiting classified information¹¹².

Strategy 2 – Investment in regulation and industrial development

Yet it is not simply in targeting and kinetic effect that education and transparency will enhance the value and influence of UAS in the future force. As identified earlier in this paper, as UAS become integrated into civilian airspace, public perception is likely to become more favourable. No longer predominately the vilified objects of war, the public is likely to increasingly see larger UA involved in delivering services and functions desired by the community, whether that be law enforcement, health and rescue, survey, or transport services. It is likely this progress can be catalysed by judicious investment and innovative regulation. Such action would benefit the UK not only in terms of providing for maximised use of UA within the future force, but also in providing a degree of economic advantage by making the UK more attractive to a growing industry – much as the UK government is trying to do with the space sector and autonomous road vehicles¹¹³. This would require a far deeper cooperation between industry and civilian regulators than is currently evident. Given the constraints on public accounts, the potential economic benefits of investment in shared civil-military UA programmes offers a compelling means to both stimulate an area of rapid economic development, exploit industrial advantage as part of the UK Government's Integrated Review of strategic influence, whilst creating an environment like to reduce the cost of future military capability. Aircraft with DAA capability exist today, so the ability to exploit RPAS in UK skies is already here.

Strategy 3 – A public taxonomy of autonomy and legal/ethical accountability as a lever for international agreement

Looking beyond RPAS with specific automatic DAA capabilities, the next iterative regulatory challenge will be to integrate increasing autonomy in a way that allows for ethical and legal accountability. The current means of classifying UA is by size and weight, rather than degrees of autonomy¹¹⁴. The requirement for a new and clearly defined taxonomy of autonomy will be foundational to effective regulation. Defence is well placed to lead on such a taxonomy, as an existing stakeholder in a variety of automatic capabilities and established relationships with industry

¹¹⁰ Mayer (2009)

¹¹¹ Mayer (2009)

¹¹² Lee (2020) p11

¹¹³ UK Space Agency (2020); Griffin (2017)

¹¹⁴ UK MOD *JDP0-30.2* (2020); [UK CAA CAP722/722A](#) (2019)

– with British firms already exploring increasing levels of autonomy.¹¹⁵ The taxonomy will go beyond facilitating the integration of increasingly autonomous UA into UK airspace, and will provide a foundational position for the UK to lead international regulation as a key component of the existing approach to emphasis rules-based systems within international relations. To do so, the taxonomy could incorporate an environmental framework within which the levels of autonomy apply¹¹⁶. This strategy would be complementary with attempts to prevent the conflation of UA with a specific use, and thereby also useful in providing an important reference for a novel regulatory approach and investment in the civil UA industry.

¹¹⁵ Burt (2018)

¹¹⁶ Massie (2016b)

Cross-Domain Considerations

Relevance of Space and Cyber

Broadly speaking, cross-domain vulnerabilities attributable to UA from the Land domain and Sea domain remain unchanged to those of inhabited aircraft. After all, a missile fired from either domain is likely to be a critical risk to an UA in the same way it would be to an inhabited aircraft with similar flight characteristics. However, the space and cyber domains do create novel vulnerabilities for UAS, in the sense that this is the only way for them to gain human input. Whereas an inhabited aircraft might have its operational capability degraded by in-flight inhibition of space or cyber capability, they generally have resilient systems that will allow the on-board crew to continue to fly the aircraft (although not always to continue the mission). Larger inhabited ISTAR aircraft also conduct on-board exploitation of sensor data, whereas UA usually leverage their wider system of datalinks to conduct real-time exploitation at third-party locations (often not even collocated with the UA flying crew)¹¹⁷. From a control perspective, UA operating within extended line of sight (LOS) usually rely on conventional radio links for remote control (common WiFi or Bluetooth protocols for the smallest systems¹¹⁸ and advanced datalinks in C-band for larger military systems¹¹⁹). Existing RPA usually exhibit limited autonomy (although often including automatic return to home capability), therefore, those operating beyond visual line of sight (BVLOS) often rely on satellite communications.

Automatic or autonomous capabilities are most vulnerable to interference in the cyber domain, whilst the BVLOS (essential for real-time flying control and data exploitation) is contingent on permissive exploitation of the space domain. The contingent liabilities for UAS in the space domain can be distinguished by those affecting aircraft operation, payload capabilities, and real-time exploitation of intelligence. Each of these is reliant in different ways on two primary capabilities – PNT and satellite communications (SATCOM) relay. The space and cyber domains are inextricably linked given that capability derived from Space is expressed within the Electromagnetic (EM) spectrum – which is a recognised interdependency of Cyber in the UK Future Force Concept¹²⁰. Future autonomy may reduce this liability, but probably not completely negate it, as for the ethical and legal ramifications discussed previously, it is likely to be desirable to have a human in the loop for lethal decisions or dynamic reprioritisation.

PNT – aircraft navigation and recovery

Both inhabited and UA utilise PNT constellations to navigate. For the UK force, this usually means the use of military-grade Global Positioning System (GPS) transmissions. Other constellations using open architecture messages (such as GLONASS and GALILEO) can augment the positional accuracy of equipment using the civilian message standard – especially useful at high latitudes due to constraints resulting from GPS orbits. Terrestrial systems such as Air Traffic Control (ATC) vectors, flight by visual references or multilateration could also enable an inhabited or remotely piloted aircraft to navigate but are likely to be harder to integrate into an UA's automatic capabilities¹²¹. To compensate for any degradation in PNT provision, an inertial navigation system (INS) is often fitted

¹¹⁷ [USAF Distributed Ground System – AN/GSQ-272 SENTINEL](#)

¹¹⁸ Yacoub *et al* (2020) p4 Table1

¹¹⁹ [GA ASI \(2020\)](#)

¹²⁰ [Joint Concept Note 1/17 \(2017\)](#)

¹²¹ Stefanski (2014);

to larger aircraft, although positional accuracy degrades over time. The INS fitted to existing RPAS is designed to be sufficiently accurate to allow automatic flight back to the vicinity of its airfield. Some current RPAS are then manually flown on approach and landing, while others do so automatically. The references for both automatic and manual landings for existing platforms are usually derived from GPS, although it would be possible to create resilience in future by creating alternative systems - interaction with conventional ILS, for example or using visual references. Such redundancies would enable UA to comprise a greater proportion of a future force. In the case of smaller UA providing a swarming capability, the US Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) have already demonstrated a simulated capability for UA to achieve mission objectives autonomously, without access to GPS or other external timing or tasking messages.¹²² However, smaller UA like these, whether unitary or operating cooperatively, will have lower endurance and range - necessitating delivery as a payload carried by a larger aircraft, which may have a greater reliance on PNT.

PNT – payload capability

PNT is not merely a contingent liability for navigation and recovery, but it is also critical to many of the operational payloads and missions that UA in a future force are likely to be asked to complete. The model of 'layered ISTAR' requires the ability to cross-cue locations between assets, which is achieved by sharing a grid reference or latitude and longitude. The ability of an aircraft to slew a sensor onto such a location is reliant upon knowing its own location to a degree of accuracy which is unlikely to be sufficiently accurate through INS provision after an extended period. If a target is acquired visually, it may be possible to strike using a laser-guided munition (which is the primary weapon type fitted to currently fielded UA) but a GPS munition would be precluded. By extension this would preclude a strike in poor weather, or in situations where laser theory presents complications such as reflectivity, absorption, or obscuration. Currently, all laser designations are conducted by a human operator – allowing the UA to do this would require significant autonomy and present increased ethical risk. Other military tasks such as survey or reconnaissance, perhaps using a synthetic aperture radar, would be more difficult to achieve without precise knowledge of their location in space and time. Negation of payload capability is not unique to UA and many inhabited aircraft would experience similar difficulties, but the ability of a human crew inside the aircraft does allow for exploitation of the 'Mk1 eyeball' even if the EM spectrum degrades PNT derived from space.¹²³ From the perspective of ISTAR rather than attack, sensor payloads, such as synthetic aperture radar or radio interception antennae, often utilise their own PNT interfaces which may be less resilient to jamming or interference than the aircraft itself.

SATCOM - aircraft

Whilst access to PNT is important to many types of UA, including some available to the public, SATCOM is currently only routinely used on a large-scale by military UA. The requirement for effective SATCOM is dependent on the level of autonomy and the required level of reach back for dynamic re-tasking. Operational RPAS (and, in the view of ICAO, those operating in shared airspace for the foreseeable future) require continuous link with the crew. Using super high frequency RF bands such as Ku or X-band, SATCOM provision is dependent on attenuation and coverage, based on

¹²² Gimber (2019); [DARPA](#)

¹²³ Colloquial military term to separate sensor derived data from that seen by the human eye.

the orbit in use¹²⁴. Without the use of SATCOM, fielded RPAS are reliant on automatic pre-programmed flight, or control via extended line of sight. *Reaper* and *Global Hawk* are two platforms which routinely operate at far greater ranges.¹²⁵ SATCOM is therefore a critical liability for current and future UA. The lack of SATCOM inhibits operational capability by constraining the range, or ability of the aircraft to change task or location. Potential mitigation has been demonstrated using airborne relay, potentially using other UA to provide the network, but this has issues with antenna accuracy.¹²⁶ An alternative may be to handover control between sequenced ground control stations operating in line of sight – but these require a considerable footprint on the ground, rendering them more expensive, less flexible and increasingly vulnerable to threats from air, land and sea.

SATCOM – real-time intelligence exploitation

Whilst increased autonomy will provide degrees of mitigation for BVLOS control, it would not allow the current model of intelligence exploitation. With current systems, the data gathered by RPAS is downlinked by SATCOM to teams of intelligence personnel distributed around the world. These Distributed Common Ground Stations (DCGS) produce real-time analysis using on-board sensors during flight, requiring considerable bandwidth over a resilient network.¹²⁷ This distributed approach also allows rapid prosecution of targets of opportunity, contingent on SATCOM availability and classified computer networks which enable operating crew, commanders and intelligence analysts to communicate during flight. However, despite this prevailing model for ISTAR and attack, there plenty of evidence that other payloads might less affected by a degradation of SATCOM. For example, Gorgon Stare Increment 2 fuses the data from 368 cameras, each of which captures 5 megapixels at 12 frames per second, over an area up to 100km².¹²⁸ The terabytes of data this produces every minute would be excessive for SATCOM transmission, necessitating algorithmic processing or post-flight exploitation.

Threats to space-based capability

Direct threats within the space domain are perhaps the most critical, with threats ranging from co-orbital or direct ascent anti-satellite attack, to exo-atmospheric nuclear bursts creating electromagnetic pulse (EMP) damage. In the case of declared anti-satellite (ASAT) weapons, each incident creates significant debris, increasing the risk of new conjunction events on orbit and increasing the risk of a runaway reaction (Kessler Syndrome)¹²⁹. Although several states have now demonstrated direct ascent ASAT weapons (China, Russia, the US and India) and any country with a nuclear-ICBM capability is theoretically capable of generating an EMP (UK, Russia, China, the US, and possibly North Korea and India), this is nonetheless perhaps the least likely of the threats due to the radical effect it would have more widely for most developed countries. With such cataclysmic potential, it is unlikely that the risk of adversaries using debris-creating explosions would be considered a reason to constrain UA in the future force. Perhaps more concerning and increasingly likely are undeclared ASAT capabilities which avoid the debris caused by legacy missile attacks.¹³⁰ The UK and US accused

¹²⁴ [UK MOD Space Primer \(2010\)](#)

¹²⁵ [Gettinger \(2019\)](#) p282

¹²⁶ [Pinkney et al \(1996\)](#);

¹²⁷ USAF (2015)

¹²⁸ Trimble (2014), as cited by Lee (2017c)

¹²⁹ Kessler and Palais (1978)

¹³⁰ [Hambling \(2020\)](#)

Russia of demonstrating one such system this year, whilst robotic tugs launched by Intelsat demonstrated a manoeuvring capability that could be used on platforms designed for co-orbital ASAT objectives.¹³¹ Mitigations for this that are likely to be available to the UK include distributed service (using allies or alternatively commercial provision), redundancy, smaller satellites or larger satellites with more fuel to outmanoeuvre a potential orbital ASAT.¹³² Given that the resilience of PNT and satellite communications is also critical to inhabited aircraft and civil infrastructure, this risk should only constrain the proportion of UA in a future force if training and equipment for inhabited alternatives prepare for such a degraded environment.

Given the technological capability required for, and escalatory nature of, direct action against satellites on orbit - the highest likelihood for interference originates from cross-domain terrestrial and cyber threats. Attacks on satellite ground stations from the land or air are the clearest forms of terrestrial cross-domain attack. These will require risk assessment and protection in the same way as other vital national infrastructure or sites of military importance, using passive and active defences as appropriate.

The most prolific threat to space-based capability in the cyber domain is from terrestrial PNT jamming of the EM spectrum. Smaller devices are readily available for purchase online (and for less than £20), and larger capabilities are actively fielded by potential adversary militaries¹³³. Perhaps more concerning, the ability for software-based spoofing to inhibit the operation or recovery of UA is postulated to have occurred with the 2011 loss of an American RQ-170 UA in Iran¹³⁴. This capability has also been demonstrated by a research team at the University of Texas.¹³⁵ This risk is not unique to UA – but has the potential to cause critical failure of communications networks, electrical grids and trading or logistical systems, worldwide¹³⁶. A sub-threshold general cyber-attack could be even more damaging – one 13-microsecond timing error at a single ground station spread worldwide in 2016, causing disruption to network broadcasts and the failure of computer systems¹³⁷. The wide-ranging consequences of spoofing GPS will render this a high priority for Defence systems and consequently it might be considered an associated risk for UA rather than a primary vulnerability. Specific hazards for UA may be mitigated by resilient design to include INS or other means of flying without reference to orbital PNT transmissions. As UA become more autonomous, they will become more able to continue their missions in the face of degraded PNT signals.

Human compromise through cyberspace

Current military RPAS, due to their resilient link to remote crews, share vulnerabilities with inhabited aircraft where to crew coercion is concerned. This is enabled by the aggregation of social and personal data online. According to UK policy (doctrinal terms in italic) these could be exploited within the *social*, *people* and *persona* layers of cyberspace, but could come from a multitude of *vectors*, with little sophistication required in *payload* or *behaviour*.¹³⁸ The ultimate *effect* is

¹³¹ Howell (2020)

¹³² Wall (2020)

¹³³ Hambling (2011); Trevithick (2017)

¹³⁴ [Faria et al \(2018\)](#); [Rawnsley \(2011\)](#); [Owano \(2011\)](#)

¹³⁵ University of Texas (2012), as cited by Lee (2017c) p239

¹³⁶ [Milner \(2020\)](#)

¹³⁷ Milner (2020)

¹³⁸ UK MOD (2016) *UK MOD Cyber Primer* p4-7, p24-25, p26

unwanted action or inaction by humans. This threat may appear to be no greater than that for inhabited aircraft, but it should be noted that there is a potential difference in vulnerability between personnel who are deployed and RPAS crews whom continue normal daily activity in their home country (those deployed often have limited access to social media). On the other hand, existing RPAS are a multi-crew environment with considerable networked infrastructure. This represents mitigation for rogue activity because a compromised individual is constrained by his peers in a way that would not be true, for example, by the pilot of a single-seat fast jet aircraft. Furthermore, although the cyber domain offers new opportunities for adversary actors to leverage, the broader risk is well understood with mitigation in place through covert activity and vetting¹³⁹. Future platforms that exhibit a higher degree of automation will see the preponderance of risk move from crews to programmers. Therefore, whilst the risk of personal compromise for existing RPAS is equivalent or less than for inhabited aircrew, there may be novel human vulnerabilities in malicious programming in the future. This will require suitable supervision and independent oversight, linked appropriately to innovative command and control systems¹⁴⁰.

Technical Compromise

Whilst the ability of the aircraft to complete its task is one facet of capability, equally significant is the ability for effective exploitation of its intelligence collection. In the case of larger military UAS, this requires a complex system of systems which exists primarily within the cyber domain. In 2011 a story broke which suggested a viral payload had reached the cockpits of UA at Creech AFB in Nevada.¹⁴¹ Given the distributed and networked nature of UAS, this could have had a dramatic effect on military outcomes. However, this may not be substantially different to the risk to inhabited aircraft in this context – as equivalent inhabited ISTAR and attack platforms are now also similarly networked.¹⁴² Smaller UA have a larger range of vulnerabilities as they lack the mitigation of larger certified RPAS or inhabited aircraft.¹⁴³

Infrastructure concerns

Cyberspace is underpinned by physical infrastructure, including typical telecommunications networks managed by nation states and international connectivity often provided by shared undersea cables. These undersea cables are often critical to continued connectivity for both military systems and civil society. There is increasing evidence that nation states exploring the potential to eavesdrop, damage or destroy these fundamental connections, including with specialist equipment such as submarines¹⁴⁴. The study of the physical connectivity of networks across the globe is an increasingly of commercial interest and several providers now provide valuable data about aggregated bandwidth, data flow and visualisations of pinch points in global networks¹⁴⁵. The safety of these networks represents a shared, major strategic concern to the most developed nations around the world, but the distributed exploitation and system of systems on which current UAS rely is more contingent on this than legacy platforms, or those with potential future autonomy.

¹³⁹ Luckey *et al* (2019)

¹⁴⁰ Sharp (2019)

¹⁴¹ Shachtman (2011)

¹⁴² [Lockheed Martin \(2020\)](#)

¹⁴³ Yaacoub *et al* (2020) p18-19

¹⁴⁴ Peach (2017); Lennon (2017) as cited in Birnbaum (2017)

¹⁴⁵ TeleGeography (2014)

Cross-domain opportunities

As well as cross-domain vulnerabilities for UA, pan-domain activity creates new opportunities. The integral role of the cyber domain and space as part of the infrastructure for UA activity is clear, but we can also leverage these domains in other ways to enhance UAS capabilities.

For example, the ability of offensive cyber activity to negate networked infrastructure designed to achieve area-access or area denial (A2/AD) may well enable UAS to achieve their objectives in what would otherwise be well-defended airspace. Few major attacks of this nature have been reported, with much cyber capability and effects remaining classified – but the success of Stuxnet provides evidence for the ability for cyber activity to degrade systems that are not continuously networked and include stand-alone and supposedly resilient systems¹⁴⁶. In the case of an integrated air defence system, this may be less risky than traditional attacks with specialist aircraft designed for suppression of enemy air defences (SEAD). This represents a potentiality within the cyber domain to generate a permissive environment for UA and increase their value within the future force. This was observed with dramatic effect in the Israeli attack on the Syrian nuclear reactor at Deir ez-Zor in 2007. This saw EW aircraft deployed inhibit Syrian air defences, in the depths of Syria with very few attacking aircraft.¹⁴⁷ There has also been academic speculation since that a hidden ‘kill switch’ was encoded onto microprocessors in the system prior to delivery and installation.¹⁴⁸ Within NATO offensive cyber activity is postulated as an extreme option, taking effect after the declaration of Article 5.¹⁴⁹ The UK’s policy on offensive cyber activity remains unclear, but there has been recent investment in the capability.¹⁵⁰

Nor is such activity limited to cyber and terrestrial domains. At an event associated with this year’s ‘DefCon’ hacker convention in Las Vegas, the US Space Force sponsored a project inviting hackers to upload software taking control of a satellite on orbit. Other challenges included creating software to change the protected characteristics of aircraft flight management systems. Whilst conducted in a controlled environment with constraints, this nonetheless demonstrated the potential for cross-domain control of uninhabited vehicles – with the hackers taking control of the satellite and photographing the moon, in contravention of its official programming.¹⁵¹

In a less kinetic example, it is possible to effect adversary behaviour by targeting their systems or leveraging the *social, people or persona* layers. Assertions about the impact of engineered social media affecting macro-outputs such as elections and referenda, or public opinion have become commonplace.¹⁵² On an individual level, military personnel are already subject to targeted scams.¹⁵³ Careless social media is likely to render it possible to associate an individual’s cyber activity with locations, times and intentions. With an effective cross-domain command and control mechanism, this could be cross-cued to an entity in a terrestrial domain for interdiction. UA, with their improved endurance leading to better persistence, can be pre-positioned in a broadly suitable area at far less

¹⁴⁶ Zetter (2014)

¹⁴⁷ Fulghum (2007) as cited by [Hounshell \(2007\)](#)

¹⁴⁸ Adee (2008) p35

¹⁴⁹ [Iftimie \(2020\)](#)

¹⁵⁰ Haynes (2018); Cook (2020)

¹⁵¹ [Mansley \(2020\)](#) on Youtube; [US Air Force Research Lab \(2020\)](#) on Youtube

¹⁵² Jarvis (2011); [Finkle \(2014\)](#)

¹⁵³ [Lange \(2019\)](#)

resource cost than inhabited aircraft for the same coverage. Therefore, UA present a good option for visually identifying an individual (using optical sensors), fixing their position and tracking them. Due to their quieter operation and smaller platform, UA are typically also more discrete.

Pan-domain command and control

To leverage such cross-domain opportunity, offensive cyber activity requires coordination with existing domains. This is identified in the UK's Future Force Concept which agrees teams operating Cyber and Electromagnetic Activities (CEMA) must be:

“multi-disciplined, highly trained (not just technically adept) and closely coordinated and deconflicted with other activity across all operational levels”.

This can be extrapolated to reflect the broader mutual dependencies affecting capabilities across all domains. As a degree of centralised control is critical to coordinating disparate agents in complex environments – there is a cogent need for coherent cross-domain command and control. There have been some suggestions that air forces are best placed to do this¹⁵⁴. Indeed, the USAF Future Operating Concept asserting that the concept of ‘air and space superiority’ is likely to shift to ‘adaptive domain control’ by 2035¹⁵⁵.

In US and UK doctrine the air domain is coordinated, for example, by a Combined Air Operations Centre (CAOC). ‘Centralised control, decentralised execution’ mandates authorities and approvals are delegated to create faster decision making and resilience to cater for hostile action. The central node remains responsible for coordinating priorities and incorporating all capabilities operating within the air domain, even those administratively controlled by the Army or Navy. In recent years, the scope of the command centre has been enlarged to incorporate activity in the space domain and the centre itself renamed to the Combined Air and Space Operations Centre. However, the recent formation of the US Space Force reminds us of the continuing challenge to balance the organisational benefits of specialist independent forces with the need for joint and integrated behaviours.

Currently, the ability of CEMA teams to coordinate activity across organisations and pan-domain is unclear. Much of the activity within the cyber domain remains classified or commercially protected. In the UK, the National Cyber Force (NCF) has grown out of a programme specified in the 2016 Cyber Security Strategy and operated jointly by the Ministry of Defence and GCHQ¹⁵⁶. Whilst the NCF is reported to be the ‘first organisation in Britain dedicated solely to offensive action against foreign adversaries’¹⁵⁷, previous offensive activity has occasionally come to light¹⁵⁸. With Cyber activity currently integrated with intelligence agencies and coordinated by the MOD in Strategic Command, it is unclear how effective coordination at an operational or tactical level can be. This has parallels to the use of Bomber Command during the Second World War – where the preponderance of attack was unavailable for coordinated activity with land or naval forces, being directed instead against identified strategic objectives. This preservation of force for strategic objectives might be desirable, but organisational structure can affect the ability to judge the relative value of independent activity

¹⁵⁴ Massie (2016)

¹⁵⁵ As cited by Massie (2016)

¹⁵⁶ UK Govt (2016)

¹⁵⁷ Wallace (2019); Sabbagh (2020); Sengupta (2020)

¹⁵⁸ [Fleming \(2018\)](#)

against cross-domain effects. The ability to shift strategic focus to support cross-domain effect suggests a need for increasingly robust pan-domain integration of space and cyber at the operational and tactical levels.

Conclusion

The evidence suggests UA are proliferating at pace, but they still face a perceptual challenge. Much of the media narrative has previously focussed on the use of UA on operations overseas, but the development of certified UA is expected to lead to a rapid increase in the size of the commercial market. Industry estimates that UA will, inside 10 years, represent more than a quarter of all commercial aircraft demonstrates the potential for a paradigm shift in public awareness and perception. Increased prevalence of UA within society is likely to change their public perception from “killer robots” and align discourse to distinctions based on role and purpose – in the same way as the public draws such distinctions between inhabited aircraft. The emergence of “good news stories” about UA providing positive community outcomes (such as support during the COVID-19 pandemic) demonstrates this potential. This is expected to translate into political advantages for those making strategic procurement decisions.

As the commercial market grows, procurement of UA for the future force are likely to become cheaper due to economies of scale. The requirement for UA possessing various levels of manoeuvrability and automation to integrate into existing airspace shows that the existing categorisation and licencing structures require change. The ICAO position (tied to historic international charter) that all such aircraft must remain remotely piloted does not address the risk of lost-link events, which indicates that national regulations are likely to drive change in the first instance, rather than international agreement. Integration of military UA into unsegregated airspace will reduce reliance on more expensive or less capable inhabited aircraft. In order to maximise competitive advantage and increase utility of UA in the future force, the UK may wish to take positive action to accelerate this, by communicating clearly the benefits of UA in a civil context, exercising leadership in permissive regulation, and making investments in the UA industry.

Embracing the use of UA in a civil context will not negate their value on the battlefield. Currently fielded UA are usually RPA but concerns about the ‘Distance Paradox’ inherent in controlling attacks from afar have raised questions about legitimacy, legality, and morality. Such concerns influence public opinion and constrain political action. Evidence suggests the UK has tried hard to change the narrative, but the idea of a ‘PlayStation mentality’ persists amongst the public. Yet there is increasing academic evidence that the nature of RPAS helps to mitigate the risk of civilian casualties and damage to non-combatant objects, rather than exacerbate it. There is also evidence of moral and psychological injury to operators who, given the nature of recent operations such as in Iraq and Syria, have not necessarily been substantially safer than their colleagues in inhabited aircraft. The accusation that UA reduce the threshold for lethal action is hard to test, but historical parallels to the use of inhabited aircraft suggest that it is the characteristics of air power more generally, rather than UA in particular, that are favoured by politicians. A negative perception of RPAS affects both the way they are presented to the public and the way they are tasked and administered within a military context. This will need to change for them to fulfil their potential in a future force. Fortunately, there is evidence of it changing already with improved recognition for RPAS crews.

Additionally, concerns about the ‘Distance Paradox’ will become less significant as the ability for UA to operate independently of a remote crew develop. This will be replaced by an “Autonomy Paradigm”, where the relative ability of a given UA to operate without human input becomes its defining characteristic. The evidence shows that the current system of categorising UA by size and weight is inadequate for the design of a regulatory system that incorporates UA into civil airspace,

because the ability of the UA to avoid other aircraft when lost-link is a key element of safety. A simple differentiator of DAA fitted or not fitted is probably also inadequate, because it does not account for different levels of manoeuvrability (such as the ability to comply with the parameters of TCAS instructions) or route selections (independent navigation when recovering lost-link). Looking beyond integration into civil airspace, the lack of an agreed taxonomy for autonomy also impinges the UK's ability to follow its broader diplomatic strategy of emphasising rules-based systems of international relations. Eight years of attempts amongst the international community to agree limitations for lethal autonomous weapon systems suggests competing demands for a new normative legal and ethical framework tied to levels of such a taxonomy. Such an international agreement is critical to maintaining the UK's stated policy on the imperative for human control of attacks. Such an approach is starkly at odds with that of other nations such as China and Turkey. Without international agreement, the UK must either change its policy, else risk being at a disadvantage.

The extent to which the UK can embrace autonomous systems will be a political decision, influenced by public opinion. It is important because autonomous systems are likely to be able to operate in contested battlespace that RPAS are denied. Crews of inhabited aircraft are likely to be more difficult to train and replace than the hardware of an UA. The advent of computers that can beat humans in complex games demonstrates that in narrowly defined rule-based engagements, autonomous algorithms are also likely to make quicker decisions than humans – outcompeting any OODA loop with a human in the chain. Some types of engagement are more procedural than others, so it is likely that the UK will benefit from a mix of RPA and increasingly autonomous UA in the future force. The advent of swarm technology also points to the ability of UA to saturate traditional ground-based air defences, based on sacrificing dispensable assets. A future UK force is therefore likely to include both sacrificial and protected UA based on role and cost.

In comparison to these ethical and perceptual challenges, the evidence suggests cross-domain liabilities of UA are more straightforward. Existing RPAS are primarily reliant on PNT and SATCOM and whilst future increasingly autonomous UA may be less reliant on SATCOM for control, it will still be critical for real-time exploitation of any data. However, the same is likely to be true for intelligence derived from networked capabilities on inhabited platforms such as the F-35. All current platforms use PNT from space so the extent to which inhabited aircraft are preferred to UA in a future force will be contingent on the extent of UA autonomy and the resilience of inhabited aircraft to degraded environments. There is no evidence that the flight management systems on modern inhabited aircraft are any more resilient to cyber-attacks than the control software for UA, although the operational structures and delegated authorities might provide an extra degree of vulnerability in the current model for RPAS employment. Similarly, there is likely to be a broadly similar cyber risk to personnel operating inhabited and uninhabited aircraft, although again this may differ based on associated factors such as whether personnel are at home or overseas.

The advent of air power saw the earliest theorists strongly advocate the strategic power of independent action by air forces. Today, some theorists suggest that we have entered an age of cyber which will allow cyber activity to win effect on its own. It is more likely that, like with air power, integrated activity will be the most powerful. Therefore, opportunities to coordinate pan-domain activity must be maximised. We already know how to manage pan-domain activity as we have done so with air, land and sea for over a hundred years. It is now time to incorporate the same

approach for the space and cyber domains. UA may not be considerably more vulnerable to space and cyber than inhabited aircraft, but perhaps they are most vulnerable in an area that is not yet considered a domain. Just as nuclear weapons changed so many paradigms for Cold War forces, autonomy in UA creates a new conceptual challenge, today.

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